

EVOLUTION OF THE CLEARING SYSTEMS IN INDIAN BANKING

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ABSTRACT

Payment system is the heart of any financial institution. They are the social infrastructures which supports all the economic activities. Hence the financial markets require a dynamic payment system which has greater option regarding safety and efficiency. Payment systems were since before known as “behind the scene activity” which means it was not of much importance. But off late a lot of importance is currently being given to improvement of the payment systems.

This paper is an effort towards finding out the evolution of this payment system, the types or instruments that are there for making this payment system what it is now. Also to analyses and find the history and evolution of cheque clearing system, which is the main non cash payment system in India.

Keywords: Payment system, clearing system

INTRODUCTION:

Payments are an integral part of the financial system. It is the soul of any transactions that take place in the economy, let it be business to consumer or consumer to business or be it business to business. A payment system is the backbone of any advanced monetary economy and hence it is essential that payment systems of the country should be “Safe, secure, sound, efficient, accessible and authorize “ as per the mission statement of Reserve Bank of India’s publication on Payments system in India Vision 2009-12.

OBJECTIVES:

The main objectives of the study are to know

1. The Evolution of payment system in India
2. Various Payment Instruments in India

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3. The history and evolution of cheque clearing system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Since this is a conceptual paper, the data is collected mainly through secondary sources and then analysed to meet the objectives. Also certain unstructured interviews were done with the managers of certain banks to know things in detail.

EVOLUTION OF PAYMENT SYSTEM IN INDIA:

Payment system can be traced back to the evolution of money. The earliest form of payment can be traced back to the pre-historic era of barter trade when the settlement of consideration happened through exchange of goods, cattle and latter commodities. This system, in the absence of money as a medium of exchange did not sustain for long, as the wants of the two parties were quite varied and did not meet their expectations. Subsequently, more formalized payment instruments developed such as coins. These were either punch-marked or cast in silver or copper. Even the coins were made out of leather too. Hence, with the birth of institutionalized forms of money, that is in the form of coins initially and later on in the form of paper money, the barter trade died off and the currency grew in importance and became the order of the day.

In ancient India, during the Mauryan period, an instrument known as **adesha** was in use. This was an order to a banker to pay the money of the note to a third person, which is similar to the present day's bill of exchange. These instruments were extensively used during the Buddhist period too.

Loan deeds which were called **rnapatra or rnalekhya** were in use in the ancient era. These deeds continued to be used during the Mughal period too, were in they were called as **dastawez** . These **dastawez** were of two types; **dastawez-e-indultalab** which was payable on demand and the other **dastawez-e-miadi** which was payable after a stipulated time.

Another instrument which was in use during the muslim period was the pay order. These were issued from the Royal Treasury on one of the district or provincial treasuries. These were called **barattes** which in the present era represents drafts or cheques.

The most important credit instrument class of the twelfth century which has evolved in India are the **hundies**. These are still in existence as of today. These represent the oldest form of credit instrument that is in existence. There were several uses of **hundies** like

- As remittance instruments (for transferring funds from one place to another)
- As credit instruments (for borrowing money)
- As bills of exchange (for the trade transactions)

Even though the coins were in existence during the ancient era, the privilege of coining the rupee was secured by the Europeans when the coins came to be known as French, English and Dutch

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arcots. During 1835, the East India Company started the company’s Rupee to bring about uniformity of coinage over British India.

Paper money, in the modern sense can be traced back to the 18th century when the private banks and the semi-government banks issued notes. Bank of Hindoostan, a joint stock bank , established in 1770 was the first bank to issue these paper notes followed by the General Bank in Bengal and Behar and the Bengal Bank. Subsequently, in 1809 when the three presidency banks were established, the note issuing work was taken over by them and each of these banks had the right to issue notes within a certain stipulated limits. The presidency banks and the private banks introduced other payment instruments in the Indian money market. The cheques were first introduced by the Bank of Hindoostan. In 1861, with the enactment of Paper Currency Act, the Government of India was conferred with the monopoly of issue of notes, hence bringing an end to the note issues by the presidency banks. The Negotiable Instruments Act (NI Act) was enacted in 1881 which formalised the usage and characteristics of cheques, promissory notes, bills of exchange and other instruments. The Negotiable Instruments Act provides a legal frame work for non-cash and paper payment instruments in India and still continues to do so even today.

PAYMENT INSTRUMENTS IN INDIA:

1. CASH / CURRENCY PAYMENTS:

In India, cash or currency plays an important role as means of payment and is also the most widely used medium of payment and exchange. Currency notes are the legal tender in India, either for payment or for deposit to account without any limits. The habit of dependency on cash is deeply rooted in India. From the customers view point cash is viewed as a better mode of payment as compared to other modes from various aspects such as cost, acceptance, anonymity, speed, cash rebates, familiarity , having a control of spending etc.

As per RBI, the value of currency in circulation at the close of March 2014 was Rs.12,829 billion which was 10.1% more than that of March 2013. Similarly the volume was increased by 5.2% from March 2013 to end at 77 billion at March 2014. This clearly shows that cash has not lost its importance and will always be the premier mode of payment.

2. NON-CASH PAYMENTS:

There are several non-cash mode of payments that can be done. They are

a. CHEQUES:

The predominant medium of the non-cash payments in India are the paper based cheques. A cheque is a bill of exchange that is drawn on a specified banker and not expressed to be payable otherwise than on demand. Various other paper instruments that are catered to the specific payment needs are instruments like the Demand Drafts, Bankers cheque, Travellers Cheques, payment orders, payable ‘At Par’ cheques like Interest or Dividend warrants, gift cheques, refund orders etc.

b. ELECTRONIC PAYMENTS:

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The substantial increase in the volume of cheques indicated the need to upgrade the existing infrastructure of exchange and settlement from the manual to the more efficient electronic system. The meaning of electronic payment is evolving over time based on the needs of the specific period. Generally, the term electronic payments means the payment to businesses, bank or public services from the customers or the businesses, which are executed through the telecommunication system or the electronic networks with the use of modern technology. These Electronic payments are conducted in different commerce categories such as;

- Business to Business (B2B)
- Business to Consumer (B2C)
- Consumer to Business (C2B), and
- Consumer to Consumer (C2C)

The various Electronic payment instruments or methods are;

- **ELECTRONIC CLEARING SYSTEM (ECS):**

This is a retail payment system which has 2 parts, the Debit ECS system wherein it facilitates bulk receipts, that is from many to one. Which means multiple debits and a single credit Ex: Bill payments of BSNL, Loan payments of Financial institutions etc.

The second part is Credit ECS, which facilitates bulk payments, that is from one to many. This implies that certain credits are given to many recipients from one party. Ex: Dividend payment, Redemption of Mutual Funds etc. This system has been in operation by RBI from 1996-97.

- **REAL TIME GROSS SETTLEMENT SYSTEM (RTGS):**

This system has been in operation from March 2004. This is a large value fund transfer system in which the financial intermediaries can make payments for their customers as well as can make their own payments. This system allows final settlement of funds to be transferred on a continuous and transaction vice throughout the processing day. The minimum amount of money to be remitted through this system was Rs.1 lakh which was subsequently raised to Rs.2 lacs.

- **ELECTRONIC FUND TRANSFER (EFT & NEFT):**

EFT is a system hosted by RBI which helps in transferring of funds, upto Rs.5 lacs from any account at any branch of any member bank in one city to another account at any branch of the member bank in an city.

The NEFT was introduced in 2005, wherein the small retail payments are done electronically through RBI system. The maximum amount of value that could be transferred was Rs.1 lakh which has been raised to Rs.2 lakhs.

- **CARD BASED CLEARING(CBC):**

In India usage of credit & debit cards have been increasing due to its utility and convenience. Many banks have been providing customized credit & debit cards so that their businesses increase. This is an important mode of payment especially at the Point of Sale (POS) transactions.

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c. OTHER PAYMENT SYSTEMS:

○ PRE-PAID PAYMENT SYSTEMS:

These are payment instrument which facilitates purchase of goods and services with the value stored in these instruments. The stored values in these instruments are the value paid by the holders by cash, by credit card or by debit to a bank account. These pre-paid instruments can be in the form of internet wallets, smart cards, magnetic stripe cards, mobile accounts, mobile wallets, internet accounts, paper vouchers, etc.

○ MOBILE PAYMENT SYSTEM:

Is any payment where a mobile device is used to initiate, authorize and confirm an exchange of financial value in return for goods and services (Au and Kauffman, 2007). There are three different models available for mobile-payment solutions on the basis of payment (Lim, 2007):

a) Bank account based: In this model, the bank account is linked to the mobile phone number of the customer. When the customer makes an m-payment transaction with a merchant, the bank account of the customer is debited and the value is credited to the merchant account.

b) Credit card based: in this model, the credit card number is linked to the mobile phone number of the customer. When the customer makes an m-payment transaction with a merchant, the credit card is charged and the value is credited to the merchant account.

c) Telecommunication company billing based: Customers may make payment to merchants using his or her mobile phone and this may be charged to the mobile phone bills of the customer. The customer then settles the bill with the telecommunication company

○ ATMs / POINT OF SALE (POS)/ ONLINE TRANSACTIONS:

Presently, there are over 61,000 ATMs in India. Savings Bank customers can withdraw cash from any bank terminal up to 5 times in a month without being charged for the same.

There are over five lakh POS terminals in the country, which enable customers to make payments for purchases of goods and services by means of credit/debit cards.

The online payment are enabled through own payment gateways or third party service providers called intermediaries. In payment transactions involving intermediaries, these intermediaries act as the initial recipient of payments and distribute the payment to merchants. In such transactions, the customers are exposed to the uncertainty of payment as most merchants treat the payments as final on receipt from the intermediaries.

PAYMENT SYSTEMS

The Reserve Bank of India has taken many initiatives in introducing and upgrading safe and efficient modes of payment systems in the India to meet the requirements of the public in general. The main feature of a large geographic spread of the country and also the vast network

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of the branches in the Indian banking system need the logistics of collection and delivery of cheques or paper instruments. This thing of the banking structure of the country has been always kept in mind during the development of the payment systems.

The use of paper-based instruments (like cheques and drafts etc.) accounts for nearly 60% of the volume of total non-cash transactions in the country. In value terms, the share is presently around 11%. By going through this statistics, it is apt that we consider the changes that have taken place in the clearing system of these paper based instruments.

HISTORY AND EVOLUTION OF CHEQUE CLEARING SYSTEM:

Cheques in India were first introduced by Bank of Hindoostan, a joint stock company/ bank which was established in 1770. In 1827 Post Bills were introduced by British. These were the promissory notes that were issued by the bank on a distant place; the holder would be paid on acceptance after a specified particular number of days.

In 1839, buying and selling of the bills of exchange was started by the Bank of Bengal and it became a part of business to be conducted by them. In 1881, the Negotiable instruments Act (NI Act) was passed which formalized many things including the usage and characteristics of instruments such as cheque, bill of exchange & promissory note. This act was the legal framework for all the non-cash paper payment instruments in India.

With the slow & steady growth in the volumes of commerce and trade and the growing confidence of the public in the usage of cheques & other paper based instruments, the transactions through these payment instruments also grew at a rapid pace. Initially the Bank employees had to frequently walk to other banks, collect cheques and drafts, and present them to the drawee banks and then collect the cash over the counter. This brought into picture the risk of the instruments being lost in transit and also that this system could be viable only for a small volume of cheques.

As the banking system started developing, the volumes & turnover of cheques also started increasing, which created the need for an organised cheque clearing & processing system. The clearing associations were started by the banks in the presidency towns. The final settlement between member banks was done by means of cheques which were drawn upon these presidency banks. Once the Imperial Bank was set up in 1921, the settlement was effected through cheques drawn on this bank.

The clearing house rules were first adopted by the Calcutta Clearing Banks Association in 1938. This association had 25 large banks as its members & 8 sub members. There were 2 ordinary clearings on each business day excluding Saturday. This association did not cover many other banks in Calcutta & hence they started a group call the Metropolitan Banking Association with 50 members. The association conducted the Metropolitan Clearing House in 1939.

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Subsequently in 1940 they arrived at an understanding with the Calcutta Clearing House. Similarly in Bombay we had the Bombay Clearing House.

After the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) was set up under the RBI Act 1935, the clearing houses that were setup in the presidency towns were taken over by the RBI

TYPES OF CHEQUE CLEARING OR PAPER-BASED CLEARING IN BANKS:

1. TRADITIONAL CLEARING:

Daily cheque clearing was initially started in 1770 wherein the bank clerks used to meet each other to exchange their cheques and settle their dues or balances if any through cash. This system was also followed in India too wherein the bank employees used to walk to other banks with the cheques provided by their customers for clearing. These cheques were presented to the respective drawee banks and the amount was collected over the counter.

2. MANUAL CLEARING/ HAND SORT CLEARING :

As discussed previously, with the formation of clearing houses in the metropolitans and other presidential towns the settlement in cash vanished & was replaced by new system. Here the clerks or the representatives of the various banks use to meet at a central point, known as the clearing house to exchange their cheques. Once the claims on cheques were settled, the balance amount was paid by the banks through the cheques of the presidential Banks. This settlement was later changed to the respective Clearing House bank cheques or the RBI cheques.

3. CLAIM BASED SETTLEMENT SYSTEM:

The first major step to be done in the process of modernisation of payment system was the computerisation of clearing operations. The claim based settlement system (CBSS) was introduced in the early eighties at Delhi, Mumbai and Chennai. This system used Microprocessor based computer system for generating the settlement reports which were based on the input statements which had the aggregate amount of claims or cheques presented by one bank over the other in the clearing house. Due to the errors in manual sorting and balancing, the settlement & balancing of clearing cheques used to take a lot of time. Hence this system of settlement was introduced.

4. MICR CLEARING:

The Magnetic Ink Character Recognition (MICR) system or format was first developed in 1950's by Stanford Research Institute & General Electric Computer Laboratory. This is a technology wherein the cheques are processed mechanically with enhanced speed. The existing cheques were redesigned with the introduction of 9 digit MICR code line at the bottom of the cheque. These machine readable 9 digit MICR numbers identified its city, through its postal code. This also helped the clearing houses to sort the cheques based on the bank & branch wise & ultimately help the clearing house to deliver these cheques to the respective bank branches. This system was introduced in 1986 for the first time in India at Mumbai. By 1989, this MICR

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clearing system was fully operational in all the metropolitan cities. Subsequently by 1990's it was operational all over the country.

5. INTER-CITY CLEARING:

The 4 metro cities, Mumbai, Delhi, Chennai and Calcutta were covered by this 2 way inter-city clearing. As per this system, any inter-city cheques which are drawn on any of these 4 metro cities were being processed at the MICR clearing house & sent to the drawee centre to be integrated with the clearing of the local center. The extension of this system to all other major cities was called as “**Regional Grid Clearing**”.

6. MAGNETIC MEDIA BASED CLEARING SYSTEM (MMBCS):

This is also known as floppy based clearing system. This is based on the in-house software of RBI, wherein the clearing data that is the funds cleared or returned are submitted in floppies to the clearing house and based on which the clearing is conducted. This was a step towards complete automation of the MICR cheque processing & clearing system. This system covers all the different types of clearings except inter-city clearing.

7. HIGH VALUE CLEARING:

This type of clearing was first introduced on April 1989 in Chennai. This system was used to settle large value based cheques in major cities especially the ones where RBI had its branches. The banks within a certain geographical area of the clearing house used to present cheques of large value, especially above 1 lakh within a certain cut-off time to the clearing house. The return clearing is held through floppy based clearing by the close of the banking hours on the same day. With the introduction of RTGS & other electronic payment system it lost its charm & finally in March 2010, this clearing was discontinued.

8. SPEED CLEARING:

This clearing refers to the processing of the outstation cheques through local clearing. Usually the outstation cheques are sent for collection to the respective bank branches through post or courier. This cheque may take 7 to 21 days to clear and also may incur certain clearing charges. This system was introduced in June 2008. This is a part of the existing MICR Clearing, the only difference is that we can clear cheques that are drawn on core banking branches which have a branch in that city.

9. CHEQUE TRUNCATION SYSTEM (CTS):

This is a logical progression of MICR clearing because the main problem with MICR system was the physical movement of cheques. With the main objective of increasing the efficiency and reducing the cheque processing time, the cheque truncation system (CTS) was introduced. CTS is an electronic process wherein the physical cheque is stopped at the presenting bank itself and only the electronic image of the check is passed on to the paying bank. The physical cheque remains with the presenting bank itself. The paying bank cheques the image & clears the funds based on the information provided to them by the presenting bank in the form of electronic media. This system was first introduced on February 1, 2008 at NCR (National Capital Region),

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New Delhi, and presently it has been rolled out in other major regions all over India through Grid system.

CONCLUSION:

The transformation of the payments & clearing systems has been profound. With regards to payment system, from the one which was dominated by the use of the precious metals or coins to the currency issued by private banks to the government issued currency. Subsequently from the paper based instruments to the more modern instruments such as card based payments or electronic payments.

Clearing system also has gone through a vast change from the manual or hand sorted clearing to the more mechanized MICR clearing and finally to the electronic way of Cheque Truncation System (CTS).

Hence to conclude, technology has been an important element in the changing dynamics of both the payment as well as the clearing system. It has fully transformed these systems from the manual, unsafe, time consuming & costly system to one which is safe, sound, quick & efficient.

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